

Study Of Natural Convection In A Triangular Cavity Filled With Water With The Lattice Boltzmann Method For Several Inclination Angles

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Abstract : The Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) with double populations is applied to solve the steady-state laminar natural convective heat transfer in a triangular cavity filled with water. The bottom wall is heated, the wall vertical is cooled, and the inclined wall is kept adiabatic. The buoyancy effect was modeled by applying the Boussinesq approximation to the momentum equation. The fluid velocity is determined by D2Q9 LBM and the energy equation is discretized by D2Q4 LBM to compute the temperature field. Comparisons with previously published work are performed and found to be in excellent agreement. Numerical results are obtained for a wide range of parameters such as the Rayleigh number from 10^3 to 10^6 and the inclination angle from 0° to 360° . Flow and thermal fields were exhibited by means of streamlines and isotherms. It is observed that inclination angle can be used as a control parameter for heat transfer in Right-angled triangular enclosures.

Keywords : Heat transfer, inclination angle, Lattice Boltzmann Method, Nusselt number, Natural convection, Rayleigh number

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